

Atomic Law-of-Averages

Mean Capacity estimation for Shell electrons has led to a new Element alignment Table.

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Except for 1, every integer $n = 2, 3, 4, \dots, N$ may be expressed as a sum of non-negative threesomes $\{a, b, a\}$ differing by no more than 1; thus

$$n = a + b + a$$

$$2 = 1 + 0 + 1 \Rightarrow \text{He}(1,0,1)$$

$$3 = 1 + 1 + 1 \Rightarrow \text{Li}(1,1,1)$$

$$4 = 1 + 2 + 1 \Rightarrow \text{Be}(1,2,1)$$

$$5 = 2 + 1 + 2 \Rightarrow \text{B}(2,1,2)$$

$$79 = 26 + 27 + 26 \Rightarrow \text{Au}(26,27,26)$$

and so on; except for Helium, threesomes are all positive.

With n representing Atomic number - the Proton counter really - this innocuous observation lead eventually to a realignment of the Table of Elements that is truly periodic [1], leaving room for nine more Elements (see below); $n = 1$ is the standout reserved for Hydrogen, the likely beginning of it all.

1 H 100																	
2 He 101	3 Li 111	4 Be 121	5 B 212	6 C 222	7 N 232	8 O 323	9 F 333	10 Ne 343	11 Na 434	12 Mg 444	13 Al 454	14 Si 545	15 P 555	16 S 565	17 Cl 656	18 Ar 666	19 K 676
20 Ca 767	21 Sc 777	22 Ti 787	23 V 878	24 Cr 888	25 Mn 898	26 Fe 989	27 Co 999	28 Ni 9109	29 Cu 10910	30 Zn 101010	31 Ga 101110	32 Ge 111011	33 As 111111	34 Se 111211	35 Br 121112	36 Kr 121212	37 Rb 121312
38 Sr 131213	39 Y 131313	40 Zr 131413	41 Nb 141314	42 Mo 141414	43 Tc 141514	44 Ru 151415	45 Rh 151515	46 Pd 151615	47 Ag 161516	48 Cd 161616	49 In 161716	50 Sn 171617	51 Sb 171717	52 Te 171817	53 I 181718	54 Xe 181818	55 Cs 181918
56 Ba 191819	57 La 191919	58 Ce 102019	59 Pr 201920	60 Nd 202020	61 Pm 202120	62 Sm 212021	63 Eu 212121	64 Gd 212221	65 Tb 222122	66 Dy 222222	67 Ho 222322	68 Er 232223	69 Tm 232323	70 Yb 232423	71 Lu 242324	72 Hf 242424	73 Ta 242524
74 W 252425	75 Re 252525	76 Os 252625	77 Ir 262526	78 Pt 262626	79 Au 262726	80 Hg 272627	81 Tl 272727	82 Pb 272827	83 Bi 282728	84 Po 282828	85 At 282928	86 Rn 292829	87 Fr 292929	88 Ra 293029	89 Ac 302930	90 Th 303030	91 Pa 303130
92 U 313031	93 Np 313131	94 Pu 313231	95 Am 323132	96 Cm 323232	97 Bk 323332	98 Cf 333233	99 Es 333333	100 Fm 333433	101 Md 343334	102 No 343434	103 Lr 343534	104 Rf 353435	105 Db 353535	106 Sg 353635	107 Bh 363536	108 Hs 363636	109 Mt 363736
110 Ds 373637	111 Rg 373737	112 Cn 373837	113 Nh 383738	114 Fl 383838	115 Mc 383938	116 Lv 393839	117 Ts 393939	118 Og 394039	119 X1 403940	120 X2 404040	121 X3 404140	122 X4 414041	123 X5 414141	124 X6 414241	125 X7 424142	126 X8 424242	127 X9 424342

Besides aesthetics, trinome tagging allowed for a new way of balancing chemical equations [2].

Now, akin to decompositions of positive integers into sums of threesomes, Electron Shell counts offer another structured decompositions of Atomic numbers. For example, for Gold (**Au**)

$$\text{Au}(79) = \{2, 8, 18, 32, 18, 1\}$$

Simple combinatorics and the Pauli Exclusion Principle yield the maximum capacity **C** in each Shell as quadratic [3]:

$$\max(\mathbf{C}) = 2m^2, m = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots$$

Thus the set **C** is $\{2, 8, 18, 32, \dots\}$, excluding Hydrogen; Nature appears to follow a 'rack and stack' or 'fill to lowest maximal capacity first' strategy when it comes to populating electron Shells.

For a given Atomic number n , let $q_n(j)$ be an individual Shell counter; set S_n as the Shell occupancy set

$$S_n = \{q_n(1), q_n(2), q_n(3), \dots\}.$$

Obviously

$$\sum q_n(j) = n$$

The above constraints imply that $q_n(1) = 2$ for all Atoms beyond Hydrogen; thus

$$S_n = \{2, q_n(2), q_n(3), \dots\}.$$

A staircase pattern emerges when plotting the maximum $\text{Max}(S_n)$ as a function of Atomic number; the 'flats' follow the quadratic rule, increasing in duration as Elements get heavier. Nothing new so far.

A sloped staircase forms when estimating instead $\text{Mean}(S_n)$; the 'spike' is Element 46 - Palladium (?).

The sloped segment end-tags and **durations** are listed below; the set **C** shows up!

- 1 - 2 (**2**)
- 3 - 10 (**8**)
- 11 - 18 (**8**)
- 19 - 36 (**18**)
- 37 - 54 (**18**)
- 55 - 86 (**32**)
- 87 - 118 (**32**)

Let's make a Table with these Element boundaries; see next page (rotated to fit): Nature's 'Law of Averages'.

Most standard alignments are evident, horizontally and vertically.

Previously projected Elements X1 - X9 should have the Shell counts:

- X1 - (2,8,18,32,32,8,9)
- X2 - (2,8,18,32,32,8,10)
- X3 - (2,8,18,32,32,8,11)
- X4 - (2,8,18,32,32,8,12)
- X5 - (2,8,18,32,32,8,13)
- X6 - (2,8,18,32,32,8,14)
- X7 - (2,8,18,32,32,8,15)
- X8 - (2,8,18,32,32,8,16)
- X9 - (2,8,18,32,32,8,17)

References

- [1] <https://zenodo.org/records/19804658>
- [2] <https://zenodo.org/records/20088294>
- [3] Wikipedia: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electron_shell

87 Fr	55 Cs	37 Rb	19 K	11 Na	3 Li	1 H
88 Ra	56 Ba	38 Sr	20 Ca	12 Mg	4 Be	2 He
89 Ac	57 La	39 Y	21 Sc	13 Al	5 B	
90 Th	58 Ce	40 Zr	22 Ti	14 Si	6 C	
91 Pa	59 Pr	41 Nb	23 V	15 P	7 N	
92 U	60 Nd	42 Mo	24 Cr	16 S	8 O	
93 Np	61 Pm	43 Tc	25 Mn	17 Cl	9 F	
94 Pu	62 Sm	44 Ru	26 Fe	18 Ar	10 Ne	
95 Am	63 Eu	45 Rh	27 Co			
96 Cm	64 Gd	46 Pd	28 Ni			
97 Bk	65 Tb	47 Ag	29 Cu			
98 Cf	66 Dy	48 Cd	30 Zn			
99 Es	67 Ho	49 In	31 Ga			
100 Fm	68 Er	50 Sn	32 Ge			
101 Md	69 Tm	51 Sb	33 As			
102 No	70 Yb	52 Te	34 Se			
103 Lr	71 Lu	53 I	35 Br			
104 Rf	72 Hf	54 Xe	36 Kr			
105 Db	73 Ta					
106 Sg	74 W					
107 Bh	75 Re					
108 Hs	76 Os					
109 Mt	77 Ir					
110 Ds	78 Pt					
111 Rg	79 Au					
112 Cn	80 Hg					
113 Nh	81 Tl					
114 Fl	82 Pb					
115 Mc	83 Bi					
116 Lv	84 Po					
117 Ts	85 At					
118 Og	86 Tn					